

AMERICAN ACADEMIC ASSOCIATION & SOCIETY

Grades update 03/2022

M.EPh.	Master of Philosophy granted by a faith-based (ecclesiastical) university. Academic & Science » Academic Degrees
Dr. sc. js.	Doctor of Jewish Studies Academic & Science » Academic Degrees
Prof. eccl.	Ecclesiastical Professor Academic & Science » Academic Degrees
B.Ec.	Bachelor of Ecclesiastical Sciences Academic & Science
M.Ec.	M.Ec. stands for Master in Ecclesiastical Sciences. Academic & Science
DR. ECCL. PSYCH.	Doctor of ecclesiastical Psychology Research Academic & Science » Psychology
Dr. eccl. phil.	Doctor of ecclesiastical Philosophy Academic & Science » Academic Degrees
Dr. eccl. med.	Doctor of History of ecclesiastical Work in Healthcare Medical » Healthcare

Dr. eth. med.	Doctor or ethics in medicine Medical
Dr. phil. pol.	Doctor of the philosophy of politics Governmental » Politics
Dr. phil. med.	Doctor of the Philosophy of Medicine Medical
Dr. phil. ba.	Doctor of Philosophy of Business Administration Academic & Science » Academic Degrees
Dr. eccl. psy.	Doctor of ecclesiastical Psychological Counseling. Academic & Science » Psychology
Dr. soc. med.	Dr. soc. med. stands for Doctor of the social aspects of medicine. Medical